

VERB-FORMING AFFIXES IN OLD TURKIC

Zh.T. Kopbayeva

PhD Doctoral Student, Kazakh National Women’s Teacher Training University
(Almaty, Kazakhstan)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15516715>

Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется использование глаголообразующих аффиксов в древнетюркском языке. Глагол, как одна из частей речи, выражает специфическое значение и служит морфологическим показателем различных грамматических категорий. Происхождение словообразовательных суффиксов в тюркских языках можно проследить по работам Махмуда аль-Кашгари. В статье представлен углубленный анализ способов словообразования, аффиксов и значений корневых и производных слов.

Ключевые слова: древнетюркский язык, глагол, аффиксы, глаголообразующие аффиксы.

Abstract. This article explores the use of verb-forming affixes in the Old Turkic language. The verb, as one of the parts of speech, expresses a specific meaning and serves as a morphological indicator of various grammatical categories. The origin of derivational suffixes in Turkic languages can be traced back to the works of Mahmud al-Kashgari. The article provides an in-depth analysis of word formation methods, affixes, and the meanings of root and derived words.

Keywords: Old Turkic language, verb, affixes, verb-forming affixes.

In Turkic languages, the tradition of referring to suffixes as affixes has been established. Since this term includes both derivational suffixes and inflectional endings, its meaning is quite broad. According to the academic grammar of the Kazakh language, suffixes are typically classified into two main categories based on their meaning and function: derivational and inflectional [1, p.81]. The main objective of this research is to provide information specifically about derivational affixes-especially those that form verbs-and to analyze their usage. Therefore, the focus of this study is on verb-forming suffixes.

A review of the literature on derivational suffixes in Turkic languages is closely related to the works of Mahmud al-Kashgari. As the first Turkologist-linguist, al-Kashgari extensively discussed word formation processes, suffixes, and the meanings of root and derived words. Through a comparative study of Turkic languages, he was one of the first scholars to offer insights into how words were formed in our ancestral language. He identified ten letters (suffixes) used to form new verbs: a, t, s, sh, k, q, l, m, n, i [2, p.44]. He also stated:

“To simplify the task and condense the book, I developed a new and unique system that had not been previously established or known. My aim was to make this work useful, clear, and practical for users. I established several principles and created measurement models. I selected root words that formed the basis of word creation in the language of each tribe. In summary, I did this to guide the advanced learners and open a path for those who strive to ascend to higher understanding” [2, p.33]. In another section of his dictionary, al-Kashgari wrote:“In this language, verbs are formed by attaching various suffixes to the imperative form of a verb.” This observation is linked to the fact that imperative verbs often appear in their root form. In fact, in modern Kazakh, there is an ongoing discussion about the distinction between root-form verbs and imperative verbs. Throughout his Dictionary, Mahmud al-Kashgari presents many other affixes that attach to nominal and verbal roots to form new words. When a suffix carries multiple meanings, the scholar provides concrete examples to clarify them. In some cases, he compares the suffixes with their counterparts in related languages.

The in-depth study of the grammatical structure of Turkic languages began in Russia in the 19th century. Although during that period derivational suffixes were not yet explicitly

defined as such, examples were presented and supported with evidence. The study of Kazakh grammar also began during this era. Scholars such as I. Giganov, M.A. Kazembek, P.M. Melioransky, N.A. Katanov, A.K. Borovkov, N.A. Baskakov, and N.K. Dmitriev were not strictly Turkic linguists but were well-versed in the scientific development of languages. Using this knowledge, they wrote grammars of Turkic-speaking peoples. I. Giganov was the first to publish a Grammar of the Tatar Language, where he stated that derived words are formed by attaching suffixes to nouns and verbs. Following Giganov's path, M.A. Kazembek's work General Grammar of the Turkish-Tatar Language, written in the first half of the 19th century, categorized words into base roots and derived roots. He also distinguished between nouns formed from verbs—dividing them into agent nouns (indicating the doer of an action) and action nouns (indicating the action itself). Sometimes, suffixes were referred to using the terms *narashchenie* (extension) or *chastitsa* (particle).

P.M. Melioransky, who compiled a grammar of the Kazakh language, in his works A Brief Grammar of the Kazakh-Kirghiz Language, Part I: Phonetics and Etymology (St. Petersburg, 1894) and Part II: Syntax (St. Petersburg, 1897), classified all lexical units in our native language into eight parts of speech based on their semantic and morphological features. He identified several affixes that form nouns and verbs and explained their meanings using concrete examples. For instance, in this work, Melioransky describes the suffix *-kile* in the verb *tepkile* as an affix that, when attached to verb roots, indicates repetition or iteration of an action [3]. Indeed, verbs like *urgyle* (to beat repeatedly) and *sebezgile* (to sprinkle repeatedly) in our language are formed using this suffix.

The renowned Turkologist N.F. Katanov, who thoroughly studied the literature, ethnography, culture, and language of Turkic peoples, in his grammar A Study of the Uryankhai Language (Kazan, 1907), included a special section comparing Turkic languages and listed suffixes that form both nouns and verbs.

Similarly, works such as A.N. Samoylovich's Brief Educational Grammar of the Modern Ottoman-Turkish Language (Leningrad, 1925), A.K. Borovkov's Textbook of the Uyghur Language (Leningrad, 1939), and the Grammar of the Bashkir Language by V.M. Nasilov and N.K. Dmitriev (Moscow-Leningrad, 1948) present derivational suffixes along with explanations of their meanings.

A.N. Kononov paid special attention to the issues of word formation in the grammars of the Uzbek and Turkish languages. Each affix that forms nouns and verbs is discussed in detail, with linguistic evidence presented to explain their origin, transformation, development, and standardization.

A.G. Gulyamov dedicated his doctoral dissertation to the historical study of derivational suffixes in the Uzbek language [Gulyamov, Problems of Historical Word Formation in the Uzbek Language. Affixation, Part I, Tashkent, 1955]. In addition, his article On the Suffix *-la* in the Uzbek Language (Scientific Notes of the Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute, 1947, Issue I) directly relates to our research. It thoroughly reveals the historical basis and the multifaceted meanings of the suffix in question [4].

Among the studies that address the issue of word formation through suffixes in individual languages, the work of Bashkir language specialist T.N. Garipov is noteworthy. His monograph, published in 1959, examines the formation of noun words in the Bashkir language in detail [5]. Azerbaijani linguist E.V. Sevortyan authored two major works focused on the word formation of both noun and verb stems. These studies stand out in that they compare data not only from related Turkic languages but also from ancient Turkic inscriptions. Dialectal features, which are considered one of the main sources in uncovering the secrets of linguistic phenomena within the historical development of language, were also taken into account. As a result, many key issues in word formation through suffixation in Turkic languages have found their proper resolution. It is important to emphasize the scientific significance and influence of E.V. Sevortyan's work. His previously dispersed views and ideas on word formation in Turkic languages are

comprehensively presented in these two monographs. During the writing of this work, we return to his research and draw supporting evidence from them [6].

M.A. Khabichev, who studied the Karachay-Balkar language, identified five methods of forming nouns. He suggested that, in the earlier stages of linguistic development, the structure of root words followed these models: C+V+C, C+V, and V+C. At that time, due to weak differentiation between nouns and verbs, some words that were originally used in combination with roots gradually evolved into auxiliary words, and eventually into affixes [7]. In his work, the noun-forming suffixes in the Karachay-Balkar language are grouped based on their meanings and etymological relationships. The analyzed language data are compared with both ancient and modern Turkic languages. Occasionally, comparisons are made with Mongolic, Ugric-Finnic, Tungusic-Manchu, and Caucasian languages. Overall, many linguists support the idea that certain linguistic units originally functioned as full lexical words and, through the process of economization in language, transformed into auxiliary elements and later into affixes. Kazakh scholar B. Sagyndykuly, in his work *Etymological Foundations of the Development of Kazakh Lexicon*, provides irrefutable evidence and examples of how the verb *ur* (to hit), the particle *son*, and the forms *shekeyin*, *sheyin*, and *sha* evolved into affixes [8]. Additionally, the comparative analysis of the Karachay and Bashkir languages with genealogically unrelated language groups is of significant value. If meaningful connections exist between linguistic units across the Turkic languages, then the idea of a common ancestral origin of all languages holds considerable merit.

In recent years, derivational suffixes found in the language of ancient Turkic inscriptions have begun to be studied more systematically. For example, A. Esenkulov's work thoroughly covers all the derivational suffixes present in the Orkhon-Enisei and Talas inscriptions, detailing their meanings and specific uses [9]. However, suffixes found in medieval inscriptions—particularly those forming verbs—have not yet been the subject of dedicated research, aside from occasional mentions in studies of individual inscriptions. Nevertheless, in this context, the works of scholars such as Ä. Näjip, A.M. Shcherbak, E.M. Fazylov, and Ä. Quryshjanov deserve mention.

A.M. Shcherbak addresses many derivational suffixes found in monuments written in Old Uzbek and Eastern Turkic languages, explaining their meanings, usage patterns, and paths of development. He also presents valuable insights into the etymology of some of these suffixes [10, pp. 105–112].

L.S. Levitskaya, in her work on the historical morphology of the Chuvash language, groups verb-forming suffixes based on their genetic relations, highlighting how some derive from others. She notes that in many cases, it is difficult to distinguish suffixes forming verbs from nouns or adjectives, as many are universal or multifunctional. Nonetheless, she attempts to separate homonymic affixes and also includes borrowed suffixes used in Chuvash word formation. Levitskaya considers the suffixes *-la*, *-le*, *-lan*, *-len*, *-lat*, *-let*, *-las*, *-les* to be genetically related. She identifies *-la*, *-le* as productive affixes that form verbs from nouns, verbs, interjections, and onomatopoeic words. B.A. Serebrennikov, V.G. Egorov, and I.P. Pavlov have also studied the word-formation capacity of the *-la* suffix in Turkic languages. Their studies also note that the roots of suffixes like *-lan*, *-len*, *-lat*, *-let*, *-las*, *-les* trace back to *-la*, *-le*, while suffixes such as *-n*, *-t*, *-s* are interpreted as merged voice affixes. In contemporary Turkic languages, suffixes like *-lan*, *-lat*, *-las* are indivisible affixes. For example, in Kazakh, *uýlen* (to marry) does not derive from any standalone verb *uýle*. In other words, suffixes like *-lan*, *-len*, *-lat*, *-let*, *-las*, *-les* attach to nouns to form verbs. In some cases, the *-lat* form also generates figurative meanings, as seen in Chuvash examples: *ilemilet* from *ilemle* ('to decorate').

As for the *-an*, *-n* affixes, E.V. Sevortyan states that they correspond to voice affixes [6, p. 317]. Verbs derived by attaching the *-n* suffix to nouns can be classified as derived verbs because in academic grammars, voice affixes are not typically considered productive in word formation. However, recent evidence suggests that some voice suffixes may indeed have had derivational functions. On this, Chuvash language researcher L.S. Levitskaya comments: “Not all denominal verbs ending in *-p* listed in Chuvash language manuals can be unambiguously

considered derivations with this affix. In some cases, we are likely dealing with homonymous markers” [11, p. 166].

For instance, *tutan* (‘to taste’), derived from *tut* (‘taste’), is paralleled in M. Kashgari’s work where *tatğan* means ‘to taste’ or ‘to like.’ In Azerbaijani, *dadān* conveys meanings like ‘to get accustomed to’ or ‘to develop a habit.’ Verbs such as *dadaylap shauyp keldi* (‘he came galloping passionately’) and *da-daylap zhür* (‘walks with a certain rhythm’) might be semantically linked to the Azerbaijani usage. Additionally, *puran* meaning ‘to live’ or ‘to reside’ relates to words like *pur* (‘existence’), and corresponds with the Kazakh word *bar* (‘to exist’). Other Chuvash examples include *pusan* (‘to begin, to initiate’) from *pus* (‘head, beginning’), *asan* (‘to remember’) from *as* (‘memory’), and *pusan* (‘to give birth, to become free’), *asan* (‘to warm up’), *sivan* (‘to cool down’)—all considered derived verbs. However, their roots (*pusa*, *siva*, *ysy*) are no longer in active use in modern Chuvash but are preserved in other Turkic languages. For instance, in Old Turkic, *sogī-su* means ‘to cool down’, while *bosa*, *bosan*, and *bosatu* relate to the ideas of ‘releasing’ or ‘giving birth’. The verb *ysyn* (‘to heat, to warm’) may also have been derived from a noun, since adjectives like *yssy* (‘hot’) exist in Turkic languages.

This also applies to verbs like *jāpen* (‘to get wet’) and *jāre-t* (‘to wet’), from *jāre* (‘wet, moist’). Tatar dialects show similar patterns: *jābən* (‘to soak’) and *jābət* (‘to wet’), with adjectives like *japsak* (‘wet, swampy’) reflecting similar roots. These words may be etymologically connected with Kazakh terms such as *zhaby* (‘to stick’) and *zhaby* (a type of horse, e.g., “Do not choose a stallion from a *zhaby* horse”), demonstrating common linguistic ancestry [11, p. 167].

In her work, Chuvash language researcher L.S. Levitskaya also provides evidence, supported by examples, that there are verb-forming suffixes with 16 different morphs. The work identifies not only multiple morphs of a single suffix but also compound (complex) suffixes. It is considered one of the first comprehensive studies to establish the relationship between these compound suffixes and the primary affixes. As the author herself states: “The manuscript of this book was completed in 1970. Today, much of it would probably be written differently; recent advances in both Soviet and international Turkology have significantly expanded the possibilities available to historical linguists. However, the content presented in this work may still prove valuable to those who study or are interested in the issues and development of Turkic—primarily Chuvash—historical linguistics” [11, p. 3].

Regardless of when the work was written, its core content, examples, linguistic units, and their semantic significance remain highly relevant and important.

Verb-forming affixes in Old Turkic represent a crucial linguistic phenomenon for understanding the historical development and word-formation systems of Turkic languages. These affixes not only perform derivational functions but also reflect the worldview and cognitive particularities of Turkic peoples. As identified during the research, affixes such as *-ga*, *-la*, *-n*, *-t*, and others attach to various roots to generate new verbs with specific meanings. These affixes served as a foundation for the formation of many verbs in modern Turkic languages. Studying the functions and meanings of these affixes provides a deeper insight into the history of the language and its word-formation processes. Therefore, the investigation of verb-forming affixes in Old Turkic is not only of linguistic importance but also holds significant cultural and historical value.

REFERENCES

1. Qazaq Grammar. (2002). Astana: Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan.
2. Kashgari, M. (2006). *Turkic Dictionary (Diwan Lughat at-Turk)*, Vol. 1. Almaty: Sozdik-Slovar.
3. Melioransky, P. M. (1894). *Brief Grammar of the Kazakh-Kyrgyz Language, Part I: Phonetics and Etymology*. St. Petersburg.

4. Melioransky, P. M. (1897). Brief Grammar of the Kazakh-Kyrgyz Language, Part II: Syntax. St. Petersburg.
5. Gulyamov, A. (1955). Problems of Historical Word Formation in the Uzbek Language. Affixation. Part I. Tashkent.
6. Garipov, M. (1959). Nominal Word Formation in the Bashkir Language. Ufa.
7. Severtyan, E. V. (1962). Verb-Forming Affixes in the Azerbaijani Language. Moscow.
8. Khabichev, M. (1997). Nominal Word Formation in the Karachay-Balkar Language. Cherkessk.
9. Sagyndykuly, B. (1994). Etymological Foundations of the Development of the Kazakh Language Lexicon. Almaty.
10. Esenqulov, A. (1976). Affixes in Old Turkic Written Monuments. Almaty.
11. Shcherbak, A. M. (1961). Grammatical Sketch of the Language of the Turkic Texts of the 10th–13th Centuries from Eastern Turkestan. Moscow–Leningrad.
12. Levitskaya, L. S. (1986). Morphology of the Chuvash Language. Cheboksary